

SMILE

A platform for strengthening the mental health of young people

15 partners from 9 European countries

Taking Care of Mental Health of Young People

What is the SMILE project about?

We empower young people from 10 to 24 years old with the tools and knowledge they need to build resilience and mental well-being in a safe and supportive environment.

What does SMILE offer?

✔ **Serious Game:** Provides young people a safe space to explore emotions, learn and grow through fun and interactive challenges.

✔ **Awareness Mobile APP:** Equips young people with practical and helpful tips, self-care techniques, and useful information.

✔ **Decision Support System:** Offers practitioners an advanced support with evidence-based guidance to enhance care.

✔ **Knowledge Management Ecosystem Portal (KM-EP):** An open platform for the general public sharing knowledge and best practices for improved outcomes.

Nurturing Healthy Minds with SMILE

SMILE enhances youth social development and emotional intelligence through fun and engaging ways to build essential life skills

Mastering your mind

Smart thinking

Problem-solving

Connecting and Communicating

Dealing with tough times

Contact us for more information: www.horizonsmile.eu/contact/

Let's Support Each Other

- ▶ Emotional well-being
- ▶ Psychological well-being
- ▶ Social well-being
- ▶ Self-Care Strategies
- ▶ Social Connections

Stay Connected

Be part of the SMILE Community
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www.horizonsmile.eu/join-smile-community

